

Modern Marketing: A Study on the Impact of Digital Marketing and its Influence on Youth in Online Shopping

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Abstract

In the recent past and even today, we are experiencing the changes in the buying behavior, which rates high among youth. Consumer's buying behavioral aspect keeps changing when it comes to the price, features, products, quality, packaging, delivery and payment and so on. However, youth is the most complicated group to be in contact with. The buying pattern is affected due to the changes in the preference of young people because they follow a rhythm of fashion and taste according to the changing time. Hence, the marketer has to spend some cores and invest every year to identify the buying behavior of the youth. The present generation is more fascinated with internet shopping than conventional shopping. This paper highlights the impacts of digital marketing and the influence on buying behavior of youth. Convenience sampling method was used to select the sample of 50 youth from Tuticorin town. The main factors influencing and creating impact on youth are accessibility, low price, variety seeking and they can shop at anytime from anywhere, and all these factors has changed the perspectives of the marketers today.

Keywords: Digital Marketing, Youth, Online Shopping, Impact and Influence.

Introduction

Today, the marketers use very often the internet in order to endorse the goods and services towards the market place. The digital marketing often referred to online marketing, web marketing or internet marketing or search engine. It is one way of marketing, which is being used broadly by the marketers today in order to promote products or services and to reach consumers using digitalized channels. With the help of internet the young consumers can access information at any time and from any where they want. The growth of internet and the development of technology have changed not only the lives of the people but also the way they do business. Now, they use technology in markets and companies for promoting and reaching out to many young customers, to introduce the fresh products and to make the service quick, collaboration with suppliers and trade associates from all around the world. This has brought transformation from industrial society to internet society. These days, people do marketing with the help of digital media that includes mobile phones and social media networks.

Objectives

The prime objective of this paper is

- To identify the impact and influences of digit marketing on youth and
- The changes in buying behavior of the young people today.

Methodology

- Primary Data: The research is done through collection of data using questionnaire.
- Secondary Data: The secondary data were collected from books, magazines and journal.
- Sample Size: The sample size is determined 50 respondent's opinion from customers who purchase products with the help of digital marketing.

Factors that Influence the Buying Behavior of Youth

- Online Advertisement: The well known technique used in digital marketing is online advertising. It is similar to television advertisement and it uses the elements of intermission, but it uses them more creative way.
- Influencer Marketing: It is a new type of digital marketing like Instagram and Snap chat. This type of marketing has influenced the marketers very much.
- Email Marketing: It uses the e-mail for sending promotional messages to users through internet and it has a high response rate and low in cost. This has been considered one of the more effective methods of online Marketing.
- Affiliate Marketing: It is a major element of package of online marketing methods and it refers to the process of obtaining commission by promoting products or services of another company.
- Social Media Networking: This is a marketing programs usually rotate around creating unique content that attracts attention and encourages the viewer to share it with their friends on social media networks.
- Updates: It helps consumers to stay with company information updated with products or services. These days consumers themselves can access internet from anywhere and at anytime to update information about products and services.
- Engagement: Digital marketing has a greater engagement and the consumers can engage with the activities of various companies. They can visit websites, read information, make purchase and provide feedback.
- Clear cut Information: It provides you the clear cut information about the products or services. Digital marketing gives a comprehensive view to the customer about the product so that; they can rely on and make purchase.
- Comparison: Digital marketing gives the opportunity for the customer to make an easy comparison with other products or services. The companies are trying to promote their products or services through online marketing.
- 24x7 Shopping: Since, internet is available on every day; there is no limit for customer to buy products through online.
- Sharing Content: By using digital media one can easily send and receive information about the product or service to others. Digital marketing provides viewers a chance to share the content with others.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1 Demographical Characteristic of the Respondents

Variables & Categories	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Gender		
Male	30	60

Female	20	40
Total	50	100
Age		
Below 18 years	28	56
19-25 years	13	26
26-35 years	6	12
Above 35 years	3	6
Total	50	100
Professional		
Student	25	50
Graduates	15	30
Technical	8	16
Business	2	4
Total	50	100
Amount Spend		
Below Rs.5,000	32	64
Rs. 6,000 - 10,000	18	36
Rs. 11,000 - 15,000	6	12
Above Rs. 15,000	4	8
Total	50	100

The above table shows that by gender wise major 60% of the respondents were male, who prefer online purchase. According to age, it shows that 56% of respondents were below 18 years of age who use online for purchase. On the basis of profession, it shows that 50% of respondents are students. The amounts spend for per purchase in online, the table depicts that 64% of respondents spend below Rs. 5,000. Hence, these are the major respondents in demographic.

Table: 1 Demographical Characteristic of the Respondents

Table 2 Factors Motivating Online Buyers

Variables & Categories	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Availability	10	20
Variety of Products	14	28

24x7	20	40
Saves your time	6	12
Total	50	100

The above table depicts that 20% of the respondents say that the internet availability is good. 28% of the respondents say that variety of products available and 40% of the respondents say that accessibility is good and 12% of the respondents say that online purchase saves your time. Therefore, majority 40% of the respondents felt that 24x7(accessibility) is good.

Figure: 2 Factors Motivating Online Buyers

Table 3 Factors Influencing Online Shopping

Variables & Categories	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Clear Information	4	8
Shop at anywhere	18	36
Easy payment	10	20
Comparing the Products	6	12
Sharing Content	2	4
Delivery	7	14
Transparency	3	6
Total	50	100

From the above table, it is examined that 8% of the respondents say that there is clear information about the product. 36% of the respondents say that shop at anywhere and 20% of the respondents say that payment is easy and 12% of the respondents say that we can compare the product and 4% of the respondents say that they can share the information with family and colleagues. 14% of the respondents say that product delivery is good and 6% of the respondents say that there is a transparency. Hence, majority 36% of the respondents say that they can shop at anywhere.

Figure: 3 Factors Influencing Online Shopping

Findings and Suggestions

The digital marketing should concentrate on providing advertisement that attracts more female towards online shopping not only young but everyone else. The advertisement is the most and prominent tool for creating awareness and the company should give some awareness to other age groups who are not part of online buyers. Online shopping must also provide things needed for graduates, professional and business people to use and encourage them to buy in online. Though cost is cheaper in online but it is not for the entire product. Therefore, they should give offers and discount to attract many. They should keep an eye on the motivational as well as on influencing factors and show some improvements. The feedbacks have to be taken seriously by the firm and bring some improvement on issue otherwise; it is possible that they may lose the customers at anytime. To become a successful business man, you should have a good customer service and must keep up your promises.

Conclusion

Form the above study we come to know that most of them who prefer online shopping are youth. Now, the digitalization has entered into the marketing and it has changed perspectives of the online buyers. As days go by the needs of the consumers increases and preference of the consumers too keeps changing. This is due to increase in the purchasing power and the attractiveness of the innovative products. Hence, we need to update to their level in order to keep them continuously in the market.

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